
SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL FOR

**NEUROANATOMY OF THE MEKOSUCHINE
CROCODYLIAN *TRILOPHOSUCHUS RACKHAMI*
WILLIS, 1993**

**SUPPLEMENTAL DOCUMENT S1: ADDITIONAL FIGURES OF THE
TRILOPHOSUCHUS RACKHAMI HOLOTYPE SPECIMEN**

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CONTENTS OF THE SUPPLEMENTARY DOCUMENT

This supplementary document to the study titled “Neuroanatomy of the mekosuchine crocodylian *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993” contains additional figures of the endocranial elements from the holotype specimen (QMF16856) of *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993. In **Figs. S1.1–S1.4** are additional figures showing the brain endocast, cranial nerve canals, cerebral carotid vasculature canals, and endosseous labyrinths. Shown in **Figs. S1.3** and **S1.4** is the left endosseous labyrinth of QMF16856. In **Figs. S1.5–S1.11** are shown several isolated vascular and neurovascular cavities/canals as well as isolated paratympanic pneumatic recesses. In **Figs. S1.12–S1.20** are shown the non-annotated versions of **Figs. 3–5, 7–10, 12, and 13** from the main text.

Figure S1.1 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Non-annotated digital model of the brain endocast in (A) dorsal, (B) ventral, (C) right lateral, (D) left lateral, (E) anterior, and (F) posterior views. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S1.1** provided as a supplementary file.

Figure S1.2 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Non-annotated digital models of the endocranial elements in (A) dorsal, (B) ventral, (C) right lateral, (D) left lateral, (E) anterior, and (F) posterior views. Note that the cerebral carotid vasculature canals could not be reconstructed in their entirety. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S1.2** provided as a supplementary file.

A

B

C

D

E

F

5 mm

Figure S1.3 (on previous page) *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Non-annotated digital model of the left endosseous labyrinth in (A) lateral, (B) medial, (C) dorsal, (D) ventral, (E) anterior, and (F) posterior views. Note that the left endosseous labyrinth could not be reconstructed in its entirety. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S1.3** provided as a supplementary file.

Figure S1.4 (on previous page) *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Annotated digital model of the left endosseous labyrinth in (A) lateral, (B) medial, (C) dorsal, (D) ventral, (E) anterior, and (F) posterior views. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S1.4** provided as a supplementary file. Abbreviations: **asc**, anterior semicircular canal (endocast); **cc**, common crus (endocast); **cd**, cochlear duct (endocast); **fov**, fenestra ovalis; **fpr**, fenestra pseudorotunda; **lag**, lagena (endocast); **lsc**, lateral semicircular canal (endocast); **lsca**, ampulla of lateral semicircular canal (endocast); **psc**, posterior semicircular canal (endocast); **ve**, vestibule (endocast).

Figure S1.5 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Parietal in dorsal view (A) opaque digital model, (B) transparent digital model exposing the parietal pneumatic recess, and (C) the isolated parietal pneumatic recess. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S1.5** provided as a supplementary file.

Figure S1.6 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Right laterosphenoid in anterolateral view (A) opaque digital model, (B) transparent digital model exposing the laterosphenoid pneumatic recess, and (C) the isolated right laterosphenoid pneumatic recess. Left laterosphenoid in anterolateral view (D) opaque digital model, (E) transparent digital model exposing the laterosphenoid pneumatic recess, and (F) the isolated left laterosphenoid pneumatic recess. Note that the left laterosphenoid pneumatic recess could not be reconstructed in its entirety as the left laterosphenoid is incomplete. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S1.6** provided as a supplementary file.

Figure S1.7 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Right prootic in anteromedial view (A) opaque digital model, (B) transparent digital model exposing the prootic facial pneumatic recess, and (C) the isolated right prootic facial pneumatic recess. Left prootic in anteromedial view (D) opaque digital model, (E) transparent digital model exposing the prootic facial pneumatic recess, and (F) the isolated left prootic facial pneumatic recess. Note that the left prootic is fractured and less complete than the right. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S1.7** provided as a supplementary file.

Figure S1.8 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Right quadrate in lateral view (A) opaque digital model, (B) transparent digital model exposing the pneumatic recesses, and (C) the isolated pneumatic recesses within the right quadrate. Left quadrate in lateral view (D) opaque digital model, (E) transparent digital model exposing the pneumatic recesses, and (F) the isolated pneumatic recesses within the left quadrate. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S1.8** provided as a supplementary file. Abbreviations: **inf pr**, infundibular recess; **q pr**, quadrate recess; **sph**, siphonium; **stymf**, subtympanic foramen.

Figure S1.9 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Left postorbital in dorsal view (A) opaque digital model, (C) transparent digital model exposing the vascular cavity/canals, and (E) the isolated left vascular cavity/canal. Right postorbital in dorsal view (B) opaque digital model, (D) transparent digital model exposing the vascular cavity/canals, and (F) the isolated right vascular cavity/canals. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S1.9** provided as a supplementary file.

Figure S1.10 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Right jugal in lateral view (A) opaque digital model, (B) transparent digital model exposing the neurovascular cavity/canal, and (C) the isolated right neurovascular cavity/canal. Left jugal in lateral view (D) opaque digital model, (E) transparent digital model exposing the neurovascular cavity/canal, and (F) the isolated left neurovascular cavity/canal. Note that the left neurovascular cavity/canal could not be reconstructed in its entirety as the left jugal is damaged and incomplete. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S1.10** provided as a supplementary file.

Figure S1.11 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Right ectopterygoid in ventral view (A) opaque digital model, (C) transparent digital model exposing the vascular cavity/canals, and (E) the isolated right vascular cavity/canals. Left ectopterygoid in ventral view (B) opaque digital model, (D) transparent digital model exposing the vascular cavity/canals, and (F) the isolated left vascular cavity/canals. Note that both ectopterygoids have sustained damage which affects the reconstruction of their vascular cavities/canals. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S1.11** provided as a supplementary file.

Figure S1.12 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Brain endocast in (A) anterior, and (B) posterior views. For the annotated version of this figure, see Figure 3 of the main text.

A

B

10 mm

Figure S1.13 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Brain endocast in (A) dorsal, and (B) ventral views. For the annotated version of this figure, see Figure 4 of the main text.

A

B

10 mm

Figure S1.14 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Brain endocast in (A) right lateral, and (B) left lateral views. For the annotated version of this figure, see Figure 5 of the main text.

Figure S1.15 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Brain endocast, cranial nerve canals, external occipital vein canals, and cerebral carotid vasculature canals in (A) anterior, and (B) posterior views. For the annotated version of this figure, see Figure 7 of the main text.

Figure S1.16 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Brain endocast, cranial nerve canals, external occipital vein canals, and cerebral carotid vasculature canals in (A) dorsal, and (B) ventral views. For the annotated version of this figure, see Figure 8 of the main text.

A

B

10 mm

Figure S1.17 *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Brain endocast, cranial nerve canals, external occipital vein canals, and cerebral carotid vasculature canals in (A) right lateral, and (B) left lateral views. For the annotated version of this figure, see Figure 9 of the main text.

A

B

C

D

E

F

5 mm

Figure S1.18 (on previous page) *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. Right endosseous labyrinth in (A) lateral, (B) medial, (C) dorsal, (D) ventral, (E) anterior, and (F) posterior views. For the annotated version of this figure, see Figure 10 of the main text.

Figure S1.19 (on previous page) *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. (A) Transparent digital model of the cranium in dorsal view, exposing the paratympanic pneumatic system. (B) Paratympanic pneumatic system in dorsal view. (C) Transparent digital model of the cranium in posterior view, exposing the paratympanic pneumatic system. (D) Paratympanic pneumatic system in posterior view. For the annotated version of this figure, see Figure 12 of the main text.

A

20 mm

B

C

10 mm

D

Figure S1.20 (on previous page) *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, QMF16856, holotype. (A) Transparent digital model of the cranium in right lateral view, exposing the paratympanic pneumatic system. (B) Paratympanic pneumatic system in right lateral view. (C) Transparent digital model of the cranium in oblique anterodorsal view, exposing the paratympanic pneumatic system. (D) Paratympanic pneumatic system in oblique anterodorsal view. For the annotated version of this figure, see Figure 13 of the main text.

INSTITUTIONAL ABBREVIATION

QM, Queensland Museum, Brisbane, Queensland, Australia (F, fossil)

REFERENCE

Willis, P. M. A. (1993). *Trilophosuchus rackhami* gen. et sp. nov., a new crocodylian from the early Miocene limestones of Riversleigh, northwestern Queensland. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology*, 13(1), 90–98.